

Performance Evaluation with the Help of Ratio Analysis

DR. RISHIKAYSH KAAKANDIKAR

**(ASSOCIATE PROFESSOR, DEPARTMENT OF MANAGEMENT,
ZEAL COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING AND RESEARCH, NARHE, PUNE)**

AND

MISS. PRAJAKTA MALHARI SAKATE

**(PG STUDENT. DEPARTMENT OF MANAGEMENT,
ZEAL COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING AND RESEARCH, NARHE, PUNE)**

ABSTRACT:

The project is about “Performance Evaluation of TeamPlus Staffing Solution Pvt Ltd with the Help of Ratio Analysis”. It Is a Staffing solution management company. Analysis of Financial statement is more objective way to examine the financial performance as well as operational performance of a company. Financial study includes analyzing the leverage, profitability; operating proficiency and solvency for an organization. Financial ratio analysis is the significant procedure to conduct the investigation. Ratio analysis is a most important technique of reviewing and analyzing a company’s accounting reports i.e. Financial statements like P&L A/C, for performance evaluation of the company. Ratio analysis is helpful measure its past, current or expected future performance of the company. Therefore, the main reason of ratio analysis is to use info about the firm to forecast how it will fare in the future.

Keywords: Financial Ratio Analysis, Financial Management, Performance Evaluation

1. INTRODUCTION:

Ratio analysis is the tool or method of analyzing and offering the relationship of things and group of things in the reports. Ratio can help the management in its various

Functions of predicting, planning synchronization, regulation and announcement. The core reason of ratio analysis is to forecast how company will perform in the future. Another reason of analysis is to recognize the possible problem areas and solve this problem.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

1. DR. M. RAVICHANDRAN: The financial performance can be measured by using various financial tools such as profitability ratio, solvency ratio, comparative statement, etc. Based on the analysis, findings have been arrived that the company has got enough funds to meet its debts & liabilities, the income statement of the company shows sales of the company increased every year at good rate and profit also increased every year.
2. N. SABARISUDHA (2011-13): The author study of financial performance evaluation by ratio analysis at VYSYA Bank project report submitted to university of madras. In which author uses various ratios to evaluate the financial performance as well as operational performance of the bank

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To recognize the operational and financial strength and weakness or position of the business.
2. To analyze the profitability and liquidity of the business with the assistance of net profit ratio, gross profit ratio and operating ratio.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:.

Descriptive Research:

Type of research is used for this project is Descriptive research. Descriptive research is defines the characteristic of the population or phenomenon, that is begin examined. This methodology focus on what of the research subject rather than the why of the research subject.

Sources of Data:

Secondary data highlights the background understandings for primary data collection. It provides rich understandings into the research process.

Secondary data is collected with the help of following sources:

Profit and Loss accounts statements. (P&L A/C)

Balance sheet (assets and liabilities)

5.DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

1] LIQUIDITY RATIO:-

1)CURRENT RATIO :-

Current Ratio = Current Assets/Current Liabilities

PARTICULARS	2016 - 2017	2017 - 2018	2018 - 2019
CURRENT ASSETS	29,21,31,647	26,22,75,379	48,72,48,474
CURRENT LIABILITIES	19,49,77,829	21,76,70,278	29,30,24,914
RATIO	1.50	1.20	1.66

INTERPRETATION:

An above tabular and graphical presentation shows proportion of current assets and current liabilities. In year 2016-2017 the ratio is 1.5, in the year 2017-2018 the ratio is 1.2 and in the year 2018-2019 the ratio is 1.66.

In year 2018-2019 the ratio is higher as associated to previous years i.e. 1.66 and in year 2017-2018 the ratio is low as compared to these years. But in the following year 2018-2019 the ratio is improved up to 1.66. Current ratio above or greater 1 indicates that the company is having higher assets as compared to liabilities.

2)ACID TEST RATIO:

$$\text{Acid Test Ratio} = \text{Quick Assets} / \text{Current Liabilities}$$

PARTICULARS	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019
QUICK ASSETS	17,56,06,159	20,20,79,396	36,67,65,562
QUICK LIABILITIES	19,49,77,829	21,76,70,278	29,30,24,914
RATIO	0.90	0.93	1.26

INTERPRETATION:

An above tabular and graphical presentation shows proportion of quickassets and quick liabilities. In the year 2016-2017 the ratio is 0.9, in year the 2017-2018 the ratio is 0.93 and in the year 2018-2019 the ratio is higher i.e. 1.26. In the year 2018-2019 the ratio is higher as associated to previous years, and in year 2016-2017 the ratio is low compared to years. Higher quick ratio or greater than 1 quick ratio indicates that quick assets are more than quick liabilities.

3] LEVERAGE RATIO:

3)DEBT TO EQUITY RATIO:

Debt to Equity Ratio = Debt Capital/ Total Equity

PARTICULARS	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019
DEBT CAPITAL	5,43,60,365	4,61,26,499	7,65,15,428
EQUITY	55,87,340	1,39,68,350	8,69,49,090
RATIO	9.7	3.30	0.88

INTERPRETATION:

An above tabulation and graphical demonstration displays the ratio of debt capital and equity capital. In the year 2016-2017 the ratio is 9.7, in the year 2017-2018 the ratio is 3.3 and in the year 2018-2019 the ratio is 0.88.

In the year 2016-2017 the ratio higher i.e. 9.7 greater debt to equity ratio shows that the company is highly depends on debt capital. A greater debt to equity ratio shows that additional creditor financing is used than investor financing. But in 2018-2019 debt to equity ratio lesser it means in this year company used higher equity capital

4] PROFITABILITY RATIO:

4)GROSS PROFIT RATIO:

Gross Profit Ratio = Gross Profit /Sales *100

PARTICULARS	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019
GROSS PROFIT	3,51,73,888	4,50,96,783	7,37,53,609
SALES	70,27,38,022	90,63,08,004	1,11,02,84,164
RATIO	5.0	4.9	6.6

INTERPRETATION:

In above tabulation and graphical representation there is proportion of gross profit and net sales. In the year 2016-2017 the ratio is 5, in 2017-2018 the ratio is 4.9 and in 2018-2019 the ratio is 6.6. In 2018-2019 the ratio is greater i.e. 6.6, in year 2017-2018 the ratio is lesser i.e. 4.9.

Above graphical presentation shows that the gross profit is fluctuating from last three years. Overall gross profit ratio is not at standard margin.

6.FINDINGS:

1. Teamplus Staffing solution Ltd. has current ratio bigger than one it specifies that the firm is having current assets higher than current liabilities.
2. Company's acid test ratio is also bigger than one it indicates that the business is having quick assets higher than quick liabilities.

7. CONCLUSION:

Company is having assets more than liabilities therefore current ratio and acid test ratio is greater than one. Overall financial position and performance of the company is satisfactory.

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